

CRITERIA FOR THE FORMATION OF LITERARY COMPETENCE AMONG FUTURE
TEACHERS

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Abstract. *this article is one of the strategic objectives of higher education for the training of professional teachers who, according to international experience, are able to work in an innovative educational practice and introduce innovations.*

Keywords: *education, experience, socio-economic life, professional activity, future teacher.*

КРИТЕРИИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ
БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация. *данная статья является одной из стратегических задач высшего образования по подготовке профессиональных педагогов, способных, согласно международному опыту, работать в условиях инновационной образовательной практики, внедрять инновации.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, опыт, социально-экономическая жизнь, профессиональная деятельность, будущий педагог.*

The great changes that are taking place in the socio-economic life of modern society are qualitatively changing the content and character of professional activity, qualities that determine the level of socio-professional mobilization of future teachers, competitiveness (the spontaneity and unity of theoretical knowledge and practical training, professional competence, flexibility and professional mobilization, the acquisition of methods for solving professional tasks, the ability to, preparation for regular enrichment of his practical experience).

In pedagogical science, the concept of psychological and pedagogical competence is concluded that the educator achieves the highest level of results in the educational process, has high professional potential, as well as communicability and positive qualities.

In the process of education and upbringing, the personality of an educator, his professional skills are important in the formation of the potential and worldview, in which young people acquire the knowledge, manners, customs, culture and labor skills accumulated by ancestors, take their rightful place in society on the basis of life experience.

At the same time, the formation of qualities in young people that will be necessary for

solving new issues and problems arising from the demand for the period is a priority of the field of pedagogical activity. To do this, first of all, the educator himself must be composed of skills to give a new level of knowledge, to be able to engage in creative activities in accordance with changing labor and life circumstances.

Competencies required of future teachers are distinguished into the following types: – regular enrichment of their knowledge by the future teacher, readiness to improve the acquired qualifications, be able to apply all kinds of Information Communication, Information Technology and teaching tools in the educational process; – have skills and qualifications; - an realized and independent activity (positive thinking, goal setting, correct use of educational literature and additional resources); – to be able to feel responsible for their actions in initiative; – to be able to maintain a critical mind and positively deal with problem situations that arise in the course of the lesson; – to establish a pedagogical dialogue based on cooperation, mutual understanding, empathy, mutual respect and trust;-to have deep professional erudition.

The criteria for the professional erudition and ability of the future teacher include: social erudition – the ability to organize a form of effective interaction with the audience during the lesson, find a language with young people and be able to form a healthy spiritual environment. Methodological erudition is the ability to convey all knowledge, those who have seen and forgiven to young people in an understandable, fluent language, the effective use of educational technology and methods. Specialization erudition is the ability to have deep and comprehensive excellent knowledge in the field of his science and subject, to work on himself.

The heuristic thinking of the future teacher is manifested in the high level of novelty of the product created by him. This requires future teachers to have the motives, striving to solve the problems posed to them on the basis of logical analysis. Only when teachers seek to solve problems in the light of methods and techniques familiar to them does they develop the need to seek new knowledge. This need provides future teachers with the opportunity to solve problems. This need encourages prospective teachers to be active in solving problems.

Creativity regularly makes it possible to carry out actions such as going beyond the scope of a particular activity, enriching existing knowledge, developing concepts, striving to create new content, mastering knowledge that is not provided for in the curriculum.

The main criterion for assessing the results of heuristic activities formed in students consists in determining the personal-professional development of students, the possibility of comparing them with oneself at a certain period of Education. Control and evaluation of activities, results of students related to professional creative development and implementation of heuristic

tasks; a) personal and professional development of future teachers; b) creative achievements of future teachers in the process of studying pedagogical category subjects; c) provides for the development of training modules in a way that meets the requirements of qualifications and the identification of the possibilities of advancement in this process.

Each assignment offered to prospective teachers can be associated with many goals of the learning process. The main purpose of training in higher pedagogical educational institutions is to develop the creative thinking of students, to interest them in pedagogical processes. This goal is impossible to achieve with the help of standard assignments, while Standard assignments are useful and necessary for the formation of professional competencies in students, it is also required to resort to other types of assignments in order to develop creative thinking in future teachers. If heuristic assignments are provided to future teachers on time and in sufficient quantities, then the experience of creative thinking and creative thinking will effectively develop in them. Alternatively, it is necessary to avoid giving students standard assignments in large quantities. They should be presented to students, normalizing them not only from the audience, but also in pedagogical processes, in addition to the audience. Working on standard assignments in a regular way will become the basis for arming students with a type of method of activity. In such a situation, they will not have the skills to complete unfamiliar tasks.

Our observations have shown that to date, students' aspirations for the organization of pedagogical processes aimed at the creative assimilation of educational materials are not sufficiently supported pedagogically. While some professors strive to organize the educational process using heuristic methods and assignments, the experience of creative activity in students is not sufficiently formed. The main reason for this lies in the strength of the desire to fulfill laws and decisions in higher pedagogical educational institutions. As a result, in general secondary schools, teachers are not able to adequately put before students assignments that serve to develop their creativeness. Students, on the other hand, are forced to perform academic actions that are not in line with their aspirations, which are alien to them. It is considered advisable to focus on determining what students are capable of, rather than using methods to assess their knowledge.

With the help of heuristic assignments, practical forgiveness related to the formation of professional competencies in future teachers can be organized on the following topics: providing students with information about pedagogical activity of a creative nature, generating knowledge and concepts, generating an idea of the psychological aspects of creative thinking, providing knowledge about the psychological directions of personality creative thinking and the structure, modern knowledge of the formation of pedagogical heuristics and trends in development is

intended to provide students with foreign and domestic experiences. Their vision of heuristic inquiry is expanded, their competencies regarding work on heuristic assignments as well as the construction of heuristic questions are developed. And in training, the role and importance of the educator in providing heuristic research and pedagogical solutions, problematic pedagogical situations, pedagogical Solutions, results that ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical solutions, scientific approaches to substantiating adopted pedagogical Solutions, International and historical experiments in this direction, pedagogical activities of the future teacher at various stages of making decisions about pedagogical situations, as well as educational actions, forms of delimitation of solutions, formation and evaluation of solutions, selection of solutions, organization of control and evaluation of solutions, clear knowledge about the interaction of Heuristic and logical research in pedagogical activities, innovative approaches, International and historical experiments are presented.

In the process of teaching pedagogical subjects, it should be envisaged to conduct lectures and practical classes with students on a number of topics. Including: methods and methods of structuring educational material, principles of grouping and harmonizing information of pedagogical content, methods and methods of forming associative thinking in future teachers, heuristic tasks of pedagogical reflection, predicting the content of the reflex method and creative research of the teacher, specific directions of pedagogical activity of the teacher and the role of pedagogical reflection in this process.

Today, the transformation of the future teacher into a creative person is gaining special relevance for the implementation of research aimed at searching for strategies for the accelerated development of his professional competencies. Because in the traditional content of education, knowledge was presented to students as educational material and it was required to master it. And in the process of heuristic education, educational materials are presented to future teachers for completely new purposes. These materials are manifested as a product of creativity for the future teacher, ensuring his creative activity, developing professional competencies.

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